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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“MY ACE AND SEAN”

My sons, my stars, so brave, so bright,
Ace—with kindness, warm and true
Sean, with fire, takes fearless flight.
Together, the world is beautiful with you two.

The rain and storms you'll surpass.
But never walk those paths in vain.
For strength you have, and love so deep,
A bond no time or tide can sweep.

Ace, the sun—calm as the sea
Sean, the storm—strong, wild, and free
So different, yet one heart you share,
A force no shadow dares compare.

So chase your dreams, but never stray.
Too far from home, too far away.
For where you go, my heart will be.
My sons, my life, my pride, and my legacy

